

Location-Informed Edge Server Selection in Integrated Access Backhaul-Enabled 6G Networks

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Abstract—With the advent of the Rel. 16 of the 5G system (5GS), 3GPP introduced the feature of integrated access and backhaul (IAB), which enables multi-hop cellular communications for coverage extension at the radio access network (RAN). 3GPP and ETSI have also worked towards the tight integration of 5G-Advanced and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) infrastructures, targeting at seamless offloading of computation loads in the near area of user equipments (UEs). In this work, we present a benchmark analytical model that leverages the enhanced measurement capabilities of next-generation (NG)-RAN base stations (BSs) and the user equipments (UEs) towards location-informed MEC host selection in IAB-enabled 6G systems. We focus on the scenario where the UE selects between two candidate MEC hosts by pulling knowledge from the Location Management Function (LMF) on the relative positions of IAB donor BSs. Using as a key metric the *aggregate length of the end-to-end IAB path separating the UE and the candidate MEC hosts*, we derive exact and approximate expressions on the IAB path length distribution and assess the performance of a simplified yet location-informed MEC host selection strategy in IAB-enabled NG-RAN setups.

Index Terms—6G, Integrated Access Backhaul, MEC, Location-informed Network Management, Edge Server Selection

I. INTRODUCTION

For decades, the radio access network (RAN) has been governed by single-hop over-the-air cellular communications to keep the required signaling and delay overheads within acceptable limits. In parallel, the measurement capabilities of the RAN infrastructure and the User Equipment (UE) have been limited to received signal strength related measurements, such as RSRP (UE), RSRQ (UE) and RPI (RAN), primarily aiming to support location-informed user mobility and radio resource management (RRM). With the advent of the 3GPP Release 15 of the 5G System (5GS Rel. 15) and its recent 5G-Advanced amendments towards the 6G system (6GS Rel. 21+), the option for multi-hop cellular communications leveraging Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) transmissions has emerged [1]–[3]. IAB is a key innovation of 5GS, enabling cost-effective and flexible network densification, especially in urban environments where optical-based backhauling is expensive, or infeasible. In this direction, 3GPP Rel. 15 of the 5GS introduced the basic architecture for IAB describing the concepts of IAB donor and child next-generation RAN (NG-RAN) base stations (BSs). The 3GPP Rel. 16 of the 5GS introduced enhancements for dynamic topology management

and load/mobility-aware RRM, whereas the 3GPP Rel. 17 of the 5GS incorporated enhanced support for multi-hop path selection along with improved latency and reliability mechanisms for URLLC use cases. The NG-RAN measurement capabilities have also been substantially enhanced through the incorporation of fine-grained distance and angle-related measurements that fully leverage MIMO. Leveraging an enlarged suite of reference signals [4], [7], NG-RAN nodes can now better estimate the Angle-of-Arrival (AoA), relative time of arrival (RTOA), multi round-trip times (mRTT). Besides, 3GPP has recently described a comprehensive location service (LCS) architecture which, among others, includes the Location Management Function (LMF) for coordinating and processing NG-RAN/UE measurements [5]. The 6GS is envisaged to seamlessly support a plethora of emerging network applications, offloading computation-hungry tasks to multi-access edge computing (MEC) servers in the near proximity of UEs will be of paramount importance [6], [8], [9], [13]. Thus, fine-grained positioning plays an instrumental role in MEC-enabled network setups where multiple paths and servers can be targeted for computation offloading using the IAB scheme.

The most current version of the 5G-Advanced architecture involves several key components that are all together required to coordinate and form a location-informed network management pipeline towards the provisioning of MEC-empowered applications and/or services. Starting with the 3GPP core network part, the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF) handles user mobility and per-user sessions in a specific geographical area while the User Plane Function (UPF) focuses on steering the user traffic and interfacing it with the MEC-empowered infrastructure. The Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) can utilize data including location, radio conditions, and usage statistics to create actionable context towards MEC-empowered service provisioning and end-to-end network/edge/cloud orchestration. The Location Management Function (LMF) is the core entity responsible for coordinating positioning procedures, collecting measurements, performing calculations (e.g., multilateration) and providing location estimates to other parties [5], potentially via the Network Exposure Function (NEF). The LMF receives and coordinates such measurement data by NG-RAN, which includes both UEs and base stations (BSs), while it can also pull the coordinates of multiple BSs (along with PRS configurations) from the OAM.

Current literature includes a plethora of works that aim to leverage edge computing capabilities towards the seamless support of cache-enabled video streaming [10]–[12]. Computation task offloading and MEC host selection have also

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North. We also assume that the locations of tier-1 IAB donors $\mathbf{b}_{i,1}^t$ ($i \in \{1, 2\}$) are known to the LMF, provided that tier-1 IAB donor BSs connect all other IAB donor BSs to the Internet and provide direct access to the 6GS core network. Besides, although intermediate IAB donor BSs can be potentially moving [1], e.g., vehicular, NTN, or aerial IAB donor BSs, the locations of tier-1 IAB donor BSs are typically known to the OAM subsystem and can be conveyed to the LMF. We express the coordinates of the tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BS as an x- and y-axis shift with respect to the tier- n IAB donor BS in a recursive fashion as follows: $\mathbf{b}_{u,n+1}^s = \mathbf{b}_{u,n}^s + (X_{u,n+1}^s, Y_{u,n+1}^s)$ and $\mathbf{b}_{i,n+1}^t = \mathbf{b}_{i,n}^t + (X_{i,n+1}^t, Y_{i,n+1}^t)$. We do so since, in real-life practice, the 6G network nodes typically report to the LMF physical layer measurements derived with respect to the reference/pilot signals transmitted by other target NG-RAN nodes, e.g., PRS, SRS, SL, CSI [4]. If relevant measurements are available at the LMF, the x and y-axis shifts $X_{1,n}^s, Y_{1,n}^s, X_{i,n}^t$ and $Y_{i,n}^t$ can be estimated as follows:

$$X_{1,n}^s = S_{1,n} \cos(\theta_{1,n}^s), Y_{1,n}^s = S_{1,n} \sin(\theta_{1,n}^s), \quad (1)$$

$$X_{i,n}^t = T_{i,n} \cos(\theta_{i,n}^t), Y_{i,n}^t = T_{i,n} \sin(\theta_{i,n}^t), \quad (2)$$

where i) the relative polar coordinates pair $(S_{1,n}, \theta_{1,n}^s)$ denotes the estimated distance and angle between the tier- n and tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BSs of user \mathbf{u}_1 , and ii) the relative polar coordinates pair $(T_{i,n}, \theta_{i,n}^t)$ denotes the estimated distance and angle between the tier- n and tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BSs of MEC host \mathbf{h}_i . Recall that all angles are measured with respect to the true North in a counter-clockwise fashion. To simplify our exposition, in Eqs. (1)-(2), we replace the subscript n with u to indicate the relative location of the user \mathbf{u}_1 with respect to its serving IAB donor BS, i.e., $(X_{1,n}^s, Y_{1,n}^s)$ and $(S_{1,u}, \theta_{1,u}^s)$. For the same reason, we denote by $T_{i,n}$ the distance between the tier-1 IAB donor BS of the UE \mathbf{u}_1 and the tier-1 IAB donor BS of the MEC host \mathbf{h}_i . Fig. 1 includes our notation.

If the LMF has no knowledge of the relative polar coordinates of a given tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BS (w.r.t. to the tier- n IAB donor BS), it can still provide the UE with a *typical error estimate* on the location of the tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BS, assuming a symmetric normal distribution around the location of the tier- n IAB donor BS location with zero mean. Such an approach is compatible with the 3GPP Rel. 18 of the LCS architecture [5]. By letting $\sigma_{1,n+1}^s$ denote the typical error estimate for the tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BS of the UE \mathbf{u}_1 and by $\sigma_{i,n+1}^t$ the typical error estimate for the tier- $(n+1)$ IAB donor BS of the MEC host \mathbf{h}_i , respectively, both calculated with respect to the position of their tier- n IAB donor BSs, it follows that, if relevant location information is not known at the LMF, the $X_{u,n+1}^s$ and $Y_{u,n+1}^s$ are modeled as independent and normally-distributed random variables (RVs) with zero mean and standard deviation $\sigma_{1,n+1}^s$, i.e., $X_{u,n+1}^s, Y_{u,n+1}^s \sim N(0, \sigma_{1,n+1}^s)$. Similarly, $X_{i,n+1}^t, Y_{i,n+1}^t \sim N(0, \sigma_{i,n+1}^t)$. To better capture known location information at the LMF, in the subsequent analysis, we use \mathcal{J} to denote the set of 6G network nodes for which the LMF has knowledge of their relative polar coordinates with respect

to their IAB donor BS. Note that, since the locations of tier-1 IAB donor BSs are assumed to be known to the LMF, by construction $\mathbf{b}_{1,n}^s, \mathbf{b}_{i,1}^t \subseteq \mathcal{J}$.

III. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

Taking into account the standardized procedures defined in [1], [5], [6], we now turn our attention to the practical scenario where the UE's traffic is routed to the selected MEC host \mathbf{h}_i (through the 6G IAB network) as follows: a) the UE \mathbf{u}_1 forwards the traffic of its edge computing tasks to its nearest (serving) IAB donor BS, b) each intermediate IAB donor BS forwards the UE's traffic to its respective IAB donor BS across the *UE's IAB path* and up to the tier-1 IAB donor BS of the UE \mathbf{u}_1 , c) the tier-1 IAB donor BS of \mathbf{u}_1 breaks out the UE's traffic towards the tier-1 IAB donor BS of the (selected) MEC host \mathbf{h}_i , and d) the tier-1 IAB donor BS of the MEC host \mathbf{h}_i routes the UE's traffic to \mathbf{h}_i over the intermediate IAB donor BSs, leveraging the respective *MEC host's \mathbf{h}_i IAB path*. Under this viewpoint, the length of the *end-to-end* IAB path from the UE \mathbf{u}_1 to the candidate MEC host \mathbf{h}_i , which involves multi-hop cellular communications across all IAB donor BSs of the *UE's and the MEC host's \mathbf{h}_i IAB paths*, is a crucial metric for MEC host selection. Accordingly, in the sequel, we consider the following location-informed MEC host selection strategy, which accounts for location knowledge available by the LMF:

$$\text{Selected MEC Host} = \begin{cases} h_1, & \text{if } E[M_{1,1}|\mathcal{J}] > E[M_{1,2}|\mathcal{J}] \\ h_2, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $M_{1,i}$ ($i \in \{1, 2\}$) denotes the *length of the end-to-end path from user \mathbf{u}_1 to MEC host \mathbf{h}_i* that is derived by:

$$M_{1,i} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1^s} S_{1,k} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{I}_i^t} T_{i,q} \quad (4)$$

Since the LMF may not have complete knowledge on the positions of all IAB donor BSs across the *UE's IAB path*, we use $\mathcal{J}_1^s \subseteq \mathcal{P}_1^s$ to denote the subset of 6G network nodes across the *UE's IAB path* \mathcal{P}_1^s for which the LMF has location-information knowledge, i.e., the relative polar coordinates $\{(S_{1,n}, \theta_{1,n}^s)\}_{n \in \mathcal{J}_1^s}$ with respect to the subsequent IAB donor BS. We also use $\mathcal{I}_1^s(\mathcal{J})$ to denote the set of indexes of the 6G network nodes with known locations in \mathcal{J}_1^s . Following a similar approach, we define as $\mathcal{J}_i^t \subseteq \mathcal{P}_i^t$ the subset of 6G network nodes in the *MEC host's \mathbf{h}_i IAB path* \mathcal{P}_i^t for which the LMF has location information knowledge, i.e., the relative polar coordinates $\{(T_{i,n}, \theta_{i,n}^t)\}_{n \in \mathcal{J}_i^t}$ with respect to the subsequent IAB donor BS. We use $\mathcal{I}_i^t(\mathcal{J})$ to denote the set of indexes for the respective 6G nodes with known locations in \mathcal{J}_i^t . For convenience, we also define the complementary sets $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s = \mathcal{I}_1^s \setminus \mathcal{I}_1^s(\mathcal{J})$ and $\bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t = \mathcal{I}_i^t \setminus \mathcal{I}_i^t(\mathcal{J})$, which correspond the 6G network nodes across the UE and MEC host IAB paths for which the LMF can only provide a typical error estimate on their relative position around their IAB donor BSs, respectively. $|X|$ denotes the cardinality of a given set X .

Lemma 1. *Let $k \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s$ be the index of a 6G network node in the UE's IAB path \mathcal{P}_1^s , for which the LMF has no knowledge of*

its relative polar coordinates with respect to their IAB donor BS. Also, let $\sigma_{1,k+1}^s$ denote the typical error on the estimated location of the tier-(k)+1 IAB donor BS around the respective location of the tier-(k) IAB donor BS, as provided by the LMF. Then, the distance $S_{1,k+1}$ is Rayleigh-distributed with mode $\sigma_{1,k+1}^s$ with probability density function (pdf) given by $f_{S_{1,k+1}|\mathcal{J}}(s) = f_R(s; \sigma_{1,k+1}^s)$, mean by $\mu_{1,k+1}^s = \mu_R(\sigma_{1,k+1}^s)$ and variance by $v_{1,k+1}^s = v_R(\sigma_{1,k+1}^s)$, where:

$$f_R(r; \sigma) = \frac{r}{\sigma^2} \cdot e^{-\frac{r^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \mu_R(\sigma) = \sigma \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}, v_R(\sigma) = \frac{4 - \pi}{2} \sigma^2 \quad (5)$$

Similarly, let $q \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t$ be the index of a 6G network node in the UE's IAB path \mathcal{P}_i^t , for which the LMF has no knowledge of its relative polar coordinates with respect to its IAB donor BS. Also, let $\sigma_{i,q+1}^t$ denote the estimated typical error of the tier-(q+1) IAB donor BS around the location of the tier-k IAB donor BS, as provided by the LMF. Then, the distance $T_{i,q+1}$ is Rayleigh-distributed with mode $\sigma_{i,q+1}^t$ with pdf given by $f_{T_{i,q+1}|\mathcal{J}}(t) = f_R(t; \sigma_{i,q+1}^t)$, mean value by $\mu_{i,q+1}^t = \mu_R(\sigma_{i,q+1}^t)$ and variance by $v_{i,q+1}^t = v_R(\sigma_{i,q+1}^t)$.

Proof. When the LMF has no knowledge of the relative polar coordinates of a tagged 6G network node in the IAB paths, it provides the UE with an estimate of its location in the form of a typical error σ that assumes a symmetric normal distribution around the location of the respective IAB donor BS, where $\sigma = \sigma_{1,k}^s$ if the 6G network node is placed at the k-th position in the UE's IAB path \mathcal{P}_1^s and $\sigma = \sigma_{i,q}^t$ if the 6G network node is placed at the q-th position in the MEC host's \mathbf{h}_i IAB path \mathcal{P}_i^t . Now, provided that a) the distances $S_{1,k}$ and $T_{1,q}$ are derived by the magnitude (norm) of the relative x- and y-axis shifts $(X_{1,k}^s, Y_{1,k}^s)$ and $(X_{i,q}^t, Y_{i,q}^t)$ (Fig. 1), respectively, i.e., $S_{1,k} = \sqrt{(X_{1,k}^s)^2 + (Y_{1,k}^s)^2}$ and $T_{1,q} = \sqrt{(X_{i,q}^t)^2 + (Y_{i,q}^t)^2}$, and b) $X_{1,k}^s, Y_{1,k}^s, X_{i,q}^t$ and $Y_{i,q}^t$ are independent and normally-distributed RVs with $X_{u,k}^s, Y_{u,k}^s \sim N(0, \sigma_{1,k}^s)$ and $X_{i,q}^t, Y_{i,q}^t \sim N(0, \sigma_{i,q}^t)$, the distances $S_{1,k}$ and $T_{1,q}$ are Rayleigh-distributed with mode $\sigma_{1,k}^s$ and $\sigma_{i,q}^t$, respectively. \square

Theorem 1. Assuming that the UE and MEC host IAB paths are disjoint, i.e., $\mathcal{P}_1^s \cap \mathcal{P}_i^t = \emptyset$, the pdf $f_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m)$ of the distance $M_{1,i}$ between the tagged UE \mathbf{u}_1 and a candidate MEC host \mathbf{h}_i , conditioned on knowledge for the relative locations of the UE and NG-RAN nodes in \mathcal{J} , is derived by:

$$f_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m) = \int_{r=0}^{m-c} f_P(r; \{\sigma_{1,k}^s\}) f_P(m-c-r; \{\sigma_{i,q}^t\}) dr, \quad (6)$$

where $c = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1^s(\mathcal{J})} S_{1,k} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{I}_i^t(\mathcal{J})} T_{i,q}$ is constant and the function $f_P(p; \{\sigma_a\})$ is derived by:

$$f_P\left(p; \{\sigma_a\}\right) = \int_{x_1=0}^p \int_{x_2=0}^{p-x_1} \dots \int_{x_{|\mathcal{A}|}=0}^{p-\sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{A}|-1} x_k} \prod_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{A}|} f_R(x_k; \sigma_k) dx_k. \quad (7)$$

The respective cdf $F_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m)$ is derived by integrating Eq. (6) over m , whereas the respective mean $\mu_{1,i} = E[M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}]$ and variance $v_{1,i}$ are derived by Eqs. (8) and (9), respectively.

$$\mu_{1,i} = c + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1^s(\mathcal{J})} \mu_R(\sigma_{1,k}^s) + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{I}_i^t(\mathcal{J})} \mu_R(\sigma_{i,q}^t) \quad (8)$$

$$v_{1,i} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1^s(\mathcal{J})} v_R(\sigma_{1,k}^s) + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{I}_i^t(\mathcal{J})} v_R(\sigma_{i,q}^t) \quad (9)$$

Proof. We begin our proof by restructuring Eq. (4) into known (constants) and unknown RV terms as follows $M_{1,i} = c + S_1 + T_i$, i.e., depending on the location knowledge available at the LMF, where the constant $c = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1^s(\mathcal{J})} S_{1,k} + \sum_{q \in \mathcal{I}_i^t(\mathcal{J})} T_{i,q}$ isolates the known (constant) part of the UE and MEC host path lengths in Eq. (4), the composite RV $S_1 = \sum_{k \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s} S_{1,k}$ models the unknown (random) part of the UE's IAB path length and the composite RV $T_i = \sum_{q \in \{\mathcal{I}_i^t \setminus \mathcal{I}_i^s(\mathcal{J})\}} T_{i,q}$ models the unknown (random) part of the MEC host's \mathbf{h}_i IAB path. Accordingly, we define $f_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m)$:

$$f_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m) \triangleq \int_{s=0}^{\infty} \int_{t=0}^{\infty} \delta(m - c - s - t) f_{S_1, T_i|\mathcal{J}}(s, t) ds dt,$$

where the $\delta(x)$ function is applied to enforce the requirement of $m = c + s + t$. By taking into account that the UE's \mathbf{u}_1 and MEC host's \mathbf{h}_i IAB paths are disjoint, the joint distribution $f_{S_1, T_i|\mathcal{J}}(s, t)$ (conditioned on the knowledge \mathcal{J} available at the LMF) breaks into two parts as follows:

$$f_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m) = \int_{r=0}^{m-c} f_{S_1|\mathcal{J}}(r) f_{T_i|\mathcal{J}}(m - c - r) dr. \quad (10)$$

In Eq. (10), we have employed a change of variables $r = s + t$ and adapted the integration limits in line with the delta-function appearing in Eq. (10). We now expand the individual pdf expressions of the composite RVs S_1 and T_i as follows:

$$f_{S_1|\mathcal{J}}(r) = \int_{s_1=0}^r \int_{s_2=0}^{r-s_1} \dots \int_{s_{|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})|=0}^{r-\sum_{k=1}^{|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})|-1} s_k} \prod_{k=1}^{|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})|} f_R(s_k; \sigma_{1,k}^s) ds_k,$$

$$f_{T_i|\mathcal{J}}(m - c - r) =$$

$$\int_{t_1=0}^{m-c-r} \int_{t_2=0}^{m-c-r-t_1} \dots \int_{t_{|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})|=0}^{m-c-r-\sum_{q=1}^{|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})|-1} t_q} \prod_{q=1}^{|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})|} (f_R(t_q; \sigma_{i,q}^t) dt_q),$$

where our expansion takes into account that a) the relative distance RVs $\{S_{1,k}\}_{k \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})}$ and $\{T_{i,q}\}_{q \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})}$ are mutually independent and Rayleigh-distributed with different modes (Theorem 1), which entails the product of individual pdfs using f_R , b) the integration limits for the individual RVs $\{S_{1,k}\}_{k \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})}$ should comply with the requirement of $S_1 = \sum_{k \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})} S_{1,k} = r$, and c) the integration limits for the individual RVs $\{T_{i,q}\}_{q \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})}$ should comply with the requirement

of $T_i = \sum_{q \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})} T_{i,q}$. By observing that the expressions share the same structure but assume different integration limits and modes for the Rayleigh-distributed parameters involved, we define the formula in Eq. (7). This concludes our proof for the pdf of $M_{1,i}$. Note that Eq. (7) derives the pdf of the path length composed by $|\mathcal{A}|$ Rayleigh-distributed RVs with modes in $\{\sigma_a\}_{a \in \mathcal{A}}$. The proof of the cdf is straightforward by definition of the cdf. For completeness, we note that $F_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m)$ can be derived by:

$$F_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m) = \int_{r=0}^{m-c} f_{S_1|\mathcal{J}}(r) \int_{t=0}^{m-c-r} f_{T_i|\mathcal{J}}(t) dt dr, \quad (11)$$

where the inner integral corresponds to the cdf of the composite RV T_i at point $t = m - c - r$. The proof for the mean and variance of $M_{1,i}$ is also straightforward if we consider that a) the RVs $\{S_{1,k}\}_{k \in \mathcal{I}_1^s}$ and $\{T_{i,q}\}_{q \in \mathcal{I}_i^t}$ are mutually independent, b) their mean and variance are derived by Theorem 1, c) the constant value c has zero variance and adds directly to the mean, and d) by the linearity of the expectation and the fact that all involved RVs are mutually independent, the mean and variance of the composite RV $M_{1,i}$ are given by the sum of means and variances of the individual RVs involved. \square

We note that in Theorem 1, the requirement of disjoint UE and MEC host paths can be alleviated by isolating shared IAB donor BSs. We leave the proof as future work. Interestingly, Theorem 1 provides exact closed-form expressions for the mean and variance of the *end-to-end UE \mathbf{u}_1 to MEC host \mathbf{h}_i IAB path length*. Also, it provides exact yet non-closed form expressions to numerically evaluate the distribution of $M_{1,i}$. Accordingly, we now provide a closed-form approximation for the pdf and cdf expressions of Theorem 1, founded on the use of the Central Limit Theorem (CLT). Note that the respective approximations become more accurate as the number of intermediate IAB donor BSs with unknown relative locations increases along the UE and MEC host IAB paths, which is exactly the scenario where numerical integration in Eqs. (6) and (11) becomes challenging.

Corollary 1. *The pdf and cdf of the distance $M_{1,i}$ between the tagged UE \mathbf{u}_1 and a target MEC host \mathbf{h}_i , conditioned on knowledge for the relative locations of the UE and NG-RAN nodes in \mathcal{J} , can be approximated by:*

$$\tilde{f}_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi v_{1,i}}} \cdot e^{-\frac{(m-\mu_{1,i})^2}{2 \cdot v_{1,i}}} \quad (12)$$

$$\tilde{F}_{M_{1,i}|\mathcal{J}}(m) = \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{m - \mu_{1,i}}{\sqrt{2 \cdot v_{1,i}}} \right) \right], \quad (13)$$

where $\operatorname{erf}(x)$ denotes the error function evaluated at point x .

Proof. The structure of Eq. (4) indicates that the aggregate IAB path length $M_{1,i}$ is governed by the sum of the mutually independent Rayleigh-distributed RVs $\{S_{1,k}\}_{k \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})}$ and $\{T_{i,q}\}_{q \in \bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})}$ with finite mean and variance (Theorem 1). Hence, according to the classical Lindeberg–Lévy CLT, as the number of points with unknown relative location increases to

Fig. 2. Monte-Carlo (5K): Probability Density Function vs. distance m

infinity, i.e., as the cardinality $|\bar{\mathcal{I}}_1^s(\mathcal{J})| + |\bar{\mathcal{I}}_i^t(\mathcal{J})| \rightarrow \infty$, the distribution of $(M_{1,i} - \mu_{1,i})/\sqrt{v_{1,i}}$ grows to a normal distribution with zero mean and unit variance $\sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. Thus, as the number of IAB donor BSs with unknown locations grows large, the pdf and cdf of $M_{1,i}$ can be approximated by Eqs. (12)-(13). \square

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section assesses the performance gap between exact / approximate pdf expressions in Section III and plots the performance of the proposed location-informed MEC host selection strategy of Eq. (3). Depending on the knowledge available at the LMF, we focus on the following scenarios:

- **Scenario 1 (S1).** Knowledge of all tier-1 BS locations $\mathcal{J}_1 = \{b_{1,1}^s, b_{1,1}^t, b_{2,1}^t\}$.
- **Scenario 2 (S2).** Knowledge of all tier-1 BS locations and the tier-2 parent BS of the UE: $\mathcal{J}_2 = \mathcal{J}_1 \cup \{b_{1,2}^t\}$.
- **Scenario 3 (S3).** Knowledge of all tier-1 BS locations and the tier-2/-3 parent BS of the UE: $\mathcal{J}_3 = \mathcal{J}_2 \cup \{b_{1,3}^s\}$.

Fig. 2 plots the conditional pdf as estimated by Theorem 1 (blue) and Corollary 1 (green), for all three scenarios under scope, along with the actual distribution of the IAB path from the UE to the target MEC host (black), as measured by 5K Monte Carlo sample IAB topologies, assuming the system model parameters appearing in the title of Fig. 2. Interestingly, the incorporation of additional knowledge on the intermediate IAB donor BSs relative positions, i.e., moving from S1 to S3, provides more fine-grained assessment of the aggregate IAB path length separating the UE and the target MEC host. On the average, the approximate and exact expressions for the aggregate IAB path length are very close for all scenarios under scope, with the exact pdf exhibiting a longer tail.

Fig. 3 plots the mean prediction accuracy of the simple MEC host selection strategy in Eq. (3), which considers simple comparison of expected values for the UE to MEC host aggregate IAB path length conditioned on the knowledge available

at the LMF. The mean prediction accuracy is calculated by comparing the output of the MEC host selection strategy in Eq. (3) to the actual status of $M_{1,1} > M_{1,2}$ averaged over 5K Monte Carlo IAB topology samples. Interestingly, Fig. 3 illustrates that in the regime where the location uncertainty is low (low $\sigma_{1,2}^t, \sigma_{2,2}^t$ values), the MEC Host Selection strategy in Eq. (3) performs comparably better than randomly selecting a target MEC host selection, i.e., which would entail a mean prediction accuracy of about 50%. However, as the uncertainty of the MEC host's \mathbf{h}_2 location increases (x-axis $\sigma_{2,2}^t$), the simple MEC host strategy can succeed, or fail, with similar probability depending on the uncertainty of the location for MEC host \mathbf{h}_1 (modeled by the $\sigma_{1,2}^t$), i.e., check the symmetry around $y = 0.5$ of the plots for $\sigma_{1,2}^t = 50, 100$ vs $\sigma_{1,2}^t = 50, 200$. In more detail, the proposed strategy is shown to perform better than random MEC host selection for $\sigma_{2,2}^t > 100$ and $\sigma_{1,2}^t = 50, 100$ while it is also shown to fail for $\sigma_{1,2}^t = 200$. This result can be explained as follows.

When the uncertainty on the location of MEC host \mathbf{h}_1 is moderate (e.g., $\sigma_{1,2}^t = 50, 100$), the initial difference in the conditional means of Eq. (3) remains large compared to the combined variance of all the remaining Rayleigh components, i.e., the ones stemming from the unknown relative locations at the LMF. As $\sigma_{2,2}^t$ increases, the reduction in the mean gap in Eq. (3), outpaces the growth in their total standard deviation, causing the probability of correctly selecting MEC host \mathbf{h}_1 to fall sharply below 50%. Once $\sigma_{2,2}^t$ exceeds a critical variance threshold, a further increase primarily amplifies the aggregate noise (due to location uncertainty) and the standardized mean-difference moves back toward zero. At that point the overlap between the two conditional distributions grows and the selection accuracy recovers toward a fair 50%. Since both $\sigma_{1,2}^t = 50, 100$ lie below that threshold, they exhibit almost identical “dip and rise” trajectories as $\sigma_{2,2}^t$ is varied, also independent of the reference scenario. By contrast, when the uncertainty on the location of MEC host \mathbf{h}_1 is already large ($\sigma_{1,2}^t = 200$), its own variance dominates the decision-variable dispersion even for low $\sigma_{2,2}^t$ values. In this uncertainty-dominated regime, any further increase in the MEC host's \mathbf{h}_1 spread can only exacerbate the total variance without ever allowing the mean-difference to prevail. As a result, the selection accuracy declines monotonically toward 50%. This performance trend readily follows by the use of the simple expected value based MEC host selection strategy of Eq. (3), which neglects the dependence of the two RVs involved due to potentially overlapping IAB donor BSs. Future work will focus on leveraging the derived joint pdf of the two RVs $M_{1,1}$ and $M_{1,2}$ in Theorem 1 towards more accurate predictions for MEC host selection in 6G IAB.

V. CONCLUSION

We proposed a benchmark analytical model to enable the shift consumption of NG-RAN/UE measurements towards the deployment of location-informed MEC host selection in IAB-enabled 6G networks. Based on that model, we have derived the joint distribution of the aggregate end-to-end IAB path

Fig. 3. Monte-Carlo (5K): Mean Prediction Accuracy using Eq. (3)

between a tagged UE and two candidate MEC hosts, providing both exact and approximate expressions. Numerical results provided valuable yet measurable insights on key performance trade-offs present in MEC-enabled NG-RAN setups with IAB capabilities. Future work aims to process in-depth the opportunities unlocked through the joint distribution expressions and derive more accurate MEC host selection criteria.

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